

Generalized Score Distribution: A Two-Parameter Discrete Distribution Accurately Describing Responses from Quality of Experience Subjective Experiments

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Abstract—Subjective responses from Multimedia Quality Assessment (MQA) experiments are conventionally analyzed with methods not suitable for the data type these responses represent. Furthermore, obtaining subjective responses is resource intensive. Thus, a method that allows the reuse of existing responses would be beneficial. Applying improper data analysis methods leads to difficulty in interpreting results. This increases the probability of drawing erroneous conclusions. Building upon existing subjective responses is resource friendly and helps develop machine learning (ML) based visual quality predictors. In this work, we show that using a discrete model for analyzing responses from MQA subjective experiments is feasible. We indicate that our proposed Generalized Score Distribution (GSD) properly describes response distributions observed in typical MQA experiments. We also highlight interpretability of GSD parameters and indicate that the GSD outperforms the approach based on sample empirical distribution when it comes to bootstrapping. Furthermore, we provide evidence that the GSD outcompetes the state-of-the-art model both in terms of goodness-of-fit and bootstrapping capabilities. To accomplish the aforementioned objectives, we analyze more than one million subjective responses from over 30 subjective experiments. Finally, we make the code implementing the GSD model and related analyses available through our GitHub repository: <https://github.com/Qub3k/subjective-exp-consistency-check>.

Index Terms—Discrete distribution, generalised score distribution, GSD, subjective experiments, quality of experience.

I. INTRODUCTION

THERE are phenomena that require gathering opinions from a panel of people. One significant example here is the notion of Quality of Experience (QoE). Contrary to the Quality of Service (QoS), the QoE also depends on how a user

of a system perceives its performance (with the word *perceives* assuming the greatest significance here). Although technical factors do influence the QoE, ultimately, it is a subjective opinion of a user that represents the most direct indication of the QoE. (Refer to Sec. 2.2.2 of [1] for a formal definition of the QoE.)

Multimedia Quality Assessment (MQA) is a sub-field of the QoE related research activities. It focuses on understanding how people perceive quality of multimedia content as well as the effects of its processing and performance of multimedia services. It is a common and recommended [2][3] practice to organize experiments in which a panel of observers provides its opinion on the quality of multimedia materials presented. We refer to such experiments as *subjective experiments* and to the opinions provided by the panel of observers as *subjective responses*. Importantly, we narrow our discussion down to subjective experiments in which participants judge the technical reproduction quality of stimuli presented only. In other words, we do not take into account subjective experiments, where observers voice their opinions regarding the content of stimuli (e.g., plot of a story or artistic properties of an image).

Lack of access to ground truth information is an inherent feature of subjective experiments. Put differently, we observe subjective responses, but have no way of directly measuring the quality of a given stimulus. One solution to this problem is gathering a large number of responses per stimulus. By doing so, we are able to ensure that any summary statistic we use to estimate stimulus quality adequately reflects population level opinions. An increasing number of researchers are following this intuition and switching from small scale controlled experiments to large scale crowdsourcing experiments [4]. Unfortunately, switching to crowdsourcing experiments usually corresponds to less precise measurements. On the other hand, organizing large scale controlled subjective experiments

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